

Prioritised IHC concepts

Higher level IHC concepts	Included Key Concepts
Claims	
Claims about effects that are not supported by evidence from fair comparisons are not necessarily wrong, but there is an insufficient basis for believing them.	
Assumptions that treatments are safe or effective can be misleading.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Do not assume that treatments are safe. 2. Do not assume that treatments have large, dramatic effects. 3. Do not assume that comparisons are not needed.
Seemingly logical assumptions about research can be misleading.	
Seemingly logical assumptions about treatments can be misleading.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Do not assume that a treatment is better based on how new or technologically impressive it is. 5. Do not assume that a treatment is helpful or safe based on how widely used it is or has been.
Trust based on the source of a claim alone can be misleading.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. Do not assume that personal experiences alone are sufficient.
Comparisons	
To identify treatment effects, studies should make fair comparisons, designed to minimize the risk of systematic errors (biases) and random errors (the play of chance).	
Comparisons of treatments should be fair.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. Consider whether the people being compared were similar.
Reviews of the effects of treatments should be fair.	
Descriptions of effects should clearly reflect the size of the effects .	
Descriptions of effects should reflect the risk of being misled by the play of chance .	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. Be cautious of small studies.
Choices	
What to do depends on judgements about a problem, the relevance of the available evidence, and the balance of expected benefits, harms, and costs.	
Evidence should be relevant.	
Expected advantages should outweigh expected disadvantages.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 9. Weigh the benefits and savings against the harms and costs of acting or not.